

Social Media Optimization (SMO) to Improve Islamic Banks' Marketing

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ABSTRACT

Social media nowadays has a really great role in online marketing. Not only to advertise the product of the company, but also to get more personal with the customer. Companies or in this case, Islamic Banks, are eager to get more customers by using social media. But is the usage of social media already efficient? Has it already seize the right target market? The purpose of this paper is to share ideas on how to optimize social media to reach the target market more efficiently. Because to seize the right customer segments, not only the right social media is needed, but also the right timing and the right content of social media are needed. The study performed, based on public data analysis, and online survey results. To conclude, Islamic Banks in Indonesia can optimize their social media further, in order to reach the target market more efficiently.

Keywords: Social Media Optimization, Islamic Banks, Islamic Marketing

I. INTRODUCTION

Islamic banking in Indonesia from year to year has a positive significant growth. There are Bank BRI Syariah, Bank Syariah Mandiri, Bank BJB Syariah, etc. The target markets of these Islamic Banks are moslems from children age until elderly. There are Education-financing Plan, for children, Umrah and Hajj financing plan for adults and elderly, and many other financing and saving facilities in Islamic Banks. The main difference between Islamic Banks and Conventional banks are the basic rule used to run the financing program. Islamic Banks used the shariah law based on Al-Qur'an and Al-Hadith.

Indonesia is the country with the largest population of Muslims. Around 84% of the population in Indonesia is Muslims. The total population of Indonesia in 2013 is 249.9 million people. Then, approximately, Muslims in Indonesia has reached 209.9 million. Imagine how big the target market for Islamic Banking really is. There are still so many possibilities Islamic bank could seize that target market which is majority still use conventional bank. So how can we reach that target market? How can we spread our mission to convert people's bank from the conventional bank into Islamic bank?

Syariah marketing is marketing begins with creation process, supply, and value changing, cannot be contradict with agreement and principal of muamalah. There are 4 characteristics of marketing: theistic which believe the existence of Allah SWT; ethical which puts morals in the front; realistic which puts honesty and religion values in the front; humanist which is a human who do not grant all manners to gain profits¹

Characteristic of syariah marketing in online marketing is very important for these fields: theistic in business is a devotion to Allah, even doing business is a part of devotion if doing it for the sake of Allah. Ethical, is how to deliver the message well, with respect, and nicely. Realistic is delivering the products, honestly and based on the real condition. Humanist is the ability to engage social bonds between Islamic bank and the customer.

One of the easiest way to market Islamic Bank in Indonesia is by online marketing. The media used can be online ads, website, social media, etc. In this case, social media is the best way to engage customers. Not only to advert the products of Islamic Bank, but also to get closer to customer by having two-ways communication online.

Social media optimization (SMO) is the use of social media and communities to generate the publicity to increase the awareness of a product, brand or event. Types of social media involved include RSS feeds, social news and bookmarking sites, as well as social networking sites, such as Twitter, Facebook, YouTube, Instagram, and blogging sites. In general, social media optimization refers to optimizing a website and its content in terms of sharing across social media and networking sites.

With the great opportunity Islamic bank has, such as a very wide target market in Indonesia, and the lack of optimization in social media used by the Islamic Banks in Indonesia, the writer decided to share some research based on online public data, and some tricks regarding to SMO in this paper titled “Social Media Optimization (SMO) to Improve Islamic Banks’ Marketing”

II. THEORETICAL BASE

Islamic Banking and Finance

An Islamic banking and financial system exists to provide a variety of religiously acceptable financial services to the Muslim communities. In addition to this special function, the banking and financial institutions, like all other aspects of Islamic society, are expected to ‘contribute richly to the achievement of the major socio-economic goals of Islam’²

¹ Kartajaya, Hermawan dan Syakir Sula (2006), “Syariah Marketing”:28

² Chapra, M.U. (1985), “Towards a Just Monetary System, Leicester: The Islamic Foundation”:34

Islamic Marketing

A business discipline that lead to process of creation, offer, and value changing from one initiator to her or his stakeholder, in the whole process based on agreement and muamalah principal in Islam³

Characteristics of Islamic Marketing

There are 4 characteristics that can be guidance for marketer according to Kartajaya dan Sula (2006:28):

1. Theistic (rabhaniyyah), that Allah SWT always watches every activity and business is part of devotion to Allah SWT, so business is not only a matter of gaining lots of profits, but also future oriented.
2. Ethical (akhlaqiyyah), put morality and etiquette on top of everything. Etiquette in communication over internet is important to buyer. Price determination and payment method as well as fee, process to gather commodity and determine profit so party can make a deal.
3. Realistic (al-waqi'iyah), put honesty and religion value based on Prophet Muhammad SAW lesson by telling real condition of products.
4. Humanist (insaniyyah) uses good manners to gain profit. Relation between company and customer gains from giving satisfaction personally.

Social Media Marketing

Social media marketing is the process of gaining website traffic or attention through social media sites.⁴ Social media marketing programs usually center on efforts to create content that attracts attention and encourages readers to share it across their social networks. The resulting electronic word of mouth (eWoM) refers to any statement consumers share via the Internet (e.g., web sites, social networks, instant messages, news feeds) about an event, product, service, brand or company.⁵ When the underlying message spreads from user to user and presumably resonates

³ Kartajaya, Hermawan dan Syakir Sula (2006), "Syariah Marketing":26

⁴ Trattner, C., Kappe, F. (2013). "Social Stream Marketing on Facebook: A Case Study" (PDF). International Journal of Social and Humanistic Computing (IJSHC) 2 (1/2).

⁵ Kietzmann, J.H., Canhoto, A. (2013). "Bittersweet! Understanding and Managing Electronic Word of Mouth" (PDF). Journal of Public Affairs 13 (2): 146–159. doi:10.1002/pa.1470. Retrieved September 17, 2013.

because it appears to come from a trusted, third-party source, as opposed to the brand or company itself.⁶

Social Media Optimization

Social media optimization (SMO) is the use of a number of social media outlets and communities to generate publicity to increase the awareness of a product, brand or event. Types of social media involved include RSS feeds, social news and bookmarking sites, as well as social networking sites, such as Twitter, and video and blogging sites. SMO is similar to search engine optimization in that the goal is to generate traffic and awareness for a website. In general, social media optimization refers to optimizing a website and its content in terms of sharing across social media and networking sites.⁷

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A. Research Approach

This research used quantitative approach. The quantitative data found in public data such as internet, or statistic data from valid resources. This research also used descriptive case study strategy, which is based on news, articles, and analysis found in valid sources in Internet. The literature study was also done by applying theories in the cases.

B. Type and Data Sources

1. Primary Data, data which is collected directly by the writer based on observation result and public data found.

Since the research is about Islamic Banks and Social media Optimization, the writer has collected the data of Islamic Banks, the Social media used, the number of follower, likes, views, etc.

2. Secondary Data, research data such as survey conducted by survey agents, which is related to the research.

Survey found in internet, such as internet usage based on age classification in Indonesia, Islamic Banks user statistic in Indonesia, etc.

⁶ Schivinski, Bruno; Dąbrowski, D. (2013). April 2013 "The Impact of Brand Communication on Brand Equity Dimensions and Brand Purchase Intention Through Facebook". Working Paper Series A, Gdansk University of Technology, Faculty of Management and Economics 4 (4): 2–23.

⁷ Wikipedia, "Social Media Optimization (SMO)" (2015)

C. Data Analysis Technique

Data analysis is process of searching and arranging collected data systematically with data organization into category, explaining into units, synthesizing, arranging into pattern, choose which one is important and which one is going to be examined, and make conclusion (Sugiyono, 2012:244).

1. Data reduction, stage of choosing data collection through data study, and observation.
2. Data display, collected from reduction process and categorized based on problems and arranged into one pattern.
3. Verification, stage of taking conclusion based on data and has been cross-checked with points of major criteria of research focus.

IV. RESULTS

Based on primary data collected, there are 12 Islamic Banks in Indonesia, such as:

1. BRI Syariah
2. Bank Syariah Mandiri
3. BNI Syariah
4. Bank Syariah Bukopin
5. Bank Muamalat Indonesia
6. Panin Bank Syariah
7. Bank Mega Syariah
8. Bank BJB Syariah
9. Bank Victoria Syariah
10. Bank BTPN Syariah
11. BCA Syariah
12. Maybank Syariah Indonesia

In this study, the social media studied are: Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, Instagram and Youtube.

1. Facebook (Indonesia total user: 69 Million (June 2014)⁸)

No.	Bank	Facebook
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⁸ CNN Indonesia, "Berapa Jumlah Pengguna Facebook dan Twitter di Indonesia" (2015)

		Like/Friends
1	Bank BJB Syariah	75.645
2	Bank Syariah Mandiri	58.330
3	BRI Syariah	38.009
4	BNI Syariah	28.795
5	Bank Muamalat Indonesia	9.906
6	Bank BTPN Syariah	4.548
7	Bank Syariah Bukopin	1.027
8	Panin Bank Syariah	624
9	Bank Mega Syariah Indonesia	362
10	Bank Victoria Syariah	134
11	BCA Syariah	63
12	Maybank Syariah Indonesia	59

Updated: 17 June 2015

2. Twitter (Indonesia total user: 50 Million (June 2014))

No.	Bank	Twitter
		Follower
1	BRI Syariah	123.000
2	Bank Syariah Mandiri	119.000
3	BNI Syariah	109.000
4	Bank Syariah Bukopin	26.200
5	Bank Muamalat Indonesia	17.100
6	Panin Bank Syariah	2.663
7	Bank Mega Syariah Indonesia	815
8	Bank BJB Syariah	790
9	Bank Victoria Syariah	9
10	Bank BTPN Syariah	-
11	BCA Syariah	-
12	Maybank Syariah Indonesia	-

Updated: 17 June 2015

3. LinkedIn (Indonesia total user: 4 Million (2015)⁹)

No.	Bank	Linkedin
		Followers
1	Bank Syariah Mandiri	9347
2	BRI Syariah	6707
3	BNI Syariah	5535
4	Bank Muamalat Indonesia	3405
5	Bank Syariah Bukopin	2113
6	Bank Mega Syariah Indonesia	1493
7	BCA Syariah	1119
8	Maybank Syariah Indonesia	506
9	Bank Victoria Syariah	438
10	Bank BJB Syariah	-
11	Bank BTPN Syariah	-
12	Panin Bank Syariah	-

Updated: 17 June 2015

4. Instagram

No.	Bank	Instagram
		Followers
1	BRI Syariah	290
2	Bank Syariah Mandiri	230
3	Bank Syariah Bukopin	98
4	Bank Mega Syariah Indonesia	61
5	Panin Bank Syariah	11
6	Bank BJB Syariah	-
7	BNI Syariah	-
8	Bank Muamalat Indonesia	-
9	Bank BTPN Syariah	-
10	Bank Victoria Syariah	-
11	BCA Syariah	-
12	Maybank Syariah Indonesia	-

Updated: 17 June 2015

⁹ Detikinet, "Pengguna LinkedIn di Indonesia Tembus 4 Juta" (2015)

5. Youtube

No.	Bank	YouTube
		View
1	BRI Syariah	176.967
2	BNI Syariah	49.743
3	Bank Muamalat Indonesia	10.062
4	Panin Bank Syariah	487
5	Bank BJB Syariah	111
6	Bank Syariah Mandiri	-
7	Bank BTPN Syariah	-
8	Bank Syariah Bukopin	-
9	Bank Mega Syariah Indonesia	-
10	Bank Victoria Syariah	-
11	BCA Syariah	-
12	Maybank Syariah Indonesia	-

Updated: 17 June 2015

A. Research Findings

The research indicates that the social media account that Islamic Banks made, wasn't really effective since the follower/friends/viewers are relatively few. Islamic Banks social media accounts are rarely updated Even, some of the social media account left unmaintained. Social Media Optimization is needed to increase the effectiveness of the social media. There are so many ways to optimize social media and one of the best SMO techniques that can be applied is the NTFC Framework of Social Media Marketing.

NTCF Framework of Social Media Marketing¹⁰

Niche : Develop niche area to stand out from competition (differentiation)

Target : Define who the target customer is, understand what they might be interested in, find out which social media channels the customer use.

Create : Create accounts at respective social media channel, link it to the official website, and consider writing articles or make videos to establish the Islamic Banks as the best in that niche area.

Fan base: Make the customer feel important, make them as the part of the company, make the customer took part.

¹⁰ Neo, Evangeline, (2015) "Social Media Marketing" (PPT)

V. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

Conclusion

Islamic Banks in Indonesia have so many opportunities in Indonesia to seize the target market. One of the best way to reach the target market is by social media marketing. Some of the Islamic Banks has already applied the social media marketing pretty well, but most of them are not working really well. The social media accounts left outdated and unmaintained. The solution is, to apply NTCF Framework as the SMO technique.

Suggestion

1. Make a daily update, not only about the product of Islamic Banks, but it can also be dakwah about riba, and Islamic finance and muamalah knowledge. Make the content useful for the viewers/customers.
2. Hire a good designer, a well-designed website or social media postings will attract more customers.
3. Be engaging, reply to the comments, reply the messages, and always keep in touch with the customers.

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